

Kinetics of oxidation of nicotinic and isonicotinic acids by permanganate in acidic medium

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Manuscript received 7 August 2008, revised 16 January 2009, accepted 11 February 2009

Abstract : The most important feature of this study of the oxidation of nicotinic acid (Nic) and isonicotinic acid (Inic) by permanganate in acidic medium is the complete solution of the rate laws (A) for Nic and (B) for Inic by varying $[H^+]$ over an extended concentration range.

$$-d[MnO_4^-]/dt = \{k_0 K_1 [H^+] + k K_1 K_2 [H^+]^2 + k_3 K_1 K_2 K_3 [H^+]^3\} [MnO_4^-]_t [Nic]_0 / \{1 + K_1 [H^+] + K_1 K_2 [H^+]^2\} \quad (A)$$

$$-d[MnO_4^-]/dt = \{k K_2 [H^+] + k_3 K_2 K_3 [H^+]^2\} [MnO_4^-]_t [Inic] / \{1 + K_2 [H^+]\} \quad (B)$$

The relationships of the rate parameters and their values are as follows : K_1 ($NC_5H_4COO^- + H^+ \rightleftharpoons HN^+C_5H_4COO^-$ [B]), 1.78×10^4 (30°) (Nic); K_2 ($HN^+C_5H_4COO^- [B] + H^+ \rightleftharpoons HN^+C_5H_4COOH [C]$), 46.2 (30°) (Nic), 33.6 (40°) (Inic); k_0 ($[B] + MnO_4^- \rightarrow$ products), $1.56 \times 10^{-3} L mol^{-1} s^{-1}$ (30°) (Nic); k ($[C] + MnO_4^- \rightarrow$ products), 1.64×10^{-2} (30°) (Nic), $1.68 \times 10^{-3} L mol^{-1} s^{-1}$ (40°) (Inic) and $k_3 K_3$ ($[C] + HMnO_4 \rightarrow$ products), 2.02×10^{-2} (30°) (Nic), $3.2 \times 10^{-3} L^2 mol^{-2} s^{-1}$ (40°) (Inic). The reactivity of Nic was greater than that of Inic.

Keywords : Kinetics, oxidation, hydrogen ion dependence, permanganate, nicotinic acid, isonicotinic acid, *N*-protonation.

Introduction

A recent kinetics study¹ on the oxidation of nicotinamide and isonicotinamide by permanganate in acidic medium showed only the *N*-protonated species to be reactive and undergo oxidation. Whereas the oxidation of isonicotinamide became independent of $[H^+]$ when its protonation was complete, in case of nicotinamide a new pathway involving oxidation by $HMnO_4$ appeared in strongly acidic media. Since nicotinic (Nic) and isonicotinic (Inic) acids have two protonation sites, viz. ring nitrogen and $-COO^-$ group, it was of interest to study the kinetics of the oxidation of these compounds by permanganate in acidic medium to delineate the role of protonation of these sites on the rate of oxidation and on the relative reactivity of the differently protonated nicotinic/isonicotinic acid species by studying $[H^+]$ -dependence over an extended-concentration range as discussed in a review on this subject².

Previously, the kinetics of the oxidation of nicotinamide by permanganate³ and that of isonicotinate

ion by diperiodatocuprate(III)⁴ and diperiodatonickelate(IV)⁵ ions in alkaline media have been reported.

Experimental

Nicotinic and isonicotinic acids (Fluka) and their *N*-oxides (Aldrich) were used as received. Isonicotinic acid was poorly soluble even in hot water, but it was found to be soluble in acidic medium. So, its 0.2 mol L^{-1} stock solution was prepared in 0.2 mol L^{-1} $HClO_4$. The procedure for following the kinetics by estimating unreacted permanganate periodically⁶ was same as described earlier¹. The interference from intermediate Mn^{III} species was suppressed by studying kinetics in presence of 0.1 mol L^{-1} sodium fluoride^{1,7,8}. The reaction products i.e. the *N*-oxides of nicotinic and isonicotinic acids were identified by matching the UV-Visible spectra of final product solutions with the spectra of authentic samples of *N*-oxides¹. In weakly acidic media, $[H^+]$ was varied by using acetate buffer/dilute $HClO_4$ and pH was measured in each case. In strongly acidic media, $[H^+]$ was varied with the help of $HClO_4$ and $[H^+]$ was assumed to be equal to the acid added. The stoichiometry, based on *N*-oxide as oxidation product¹, is given by eq. (1).

The kinetics were studied at a fixed ionic strength of 1.0 mol L⁻¹ maintained with the help of LiClO₄. Reproducibility of the replicate rate measurements was high (within ±5.0%). All calculations were made on MS Excel.

Table 1. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} and second order rate constants, k_2 , at $I = 1.0 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ and $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.0 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$

$10^3 [\text{MnO}_4^-]$ (mol L ⁻¹)	$10^2 [\text{S}]_0$ (mol L ⁻¹)	Temp. (°C)	$10^5 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)	$10^3 k_2$ (L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
Isonicotinic acid				
1.00	2.00	40	9.12	4.56
2.00	2.00	40	9.12	4.56
2.00	4.00	40	18.33	4.58
2.00	5.00	40	21.50	4.30
2.00	2.00	35	5.75	2.87
2.00	5.00	35	13.42	2.68
2.00	2.00	45	13.36	6.65
2.00	5.00	45	34.50	6.90
Nicotinic acid				
1.00	2.00	30	57.5	28.7
2.00	2.00	30	53.7	26.8
1.00	1.00	30	32.6	32.6
1.00	2.50	30	73.3	29.3
1.00	1.00	30	29.3	29.3
1.00	1.00	35	44.2	44.2
1.00	2.50	35	105.0	42.0
1.00	1.00	40	57.5	57.5
1.00	2.50	40	140.2	56.1

Results

In the case of both the reducing acids, the kinetics displayed first order in permanganate as well as the reductant. It was studied under pseudo-first order conditions, i.e. $[\text{reductant}] \gg [\text{MnO}_4^-]$. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} were determined from $\log [\text{MnO}_4^-]_t$ versus time, t plots. The kinetics were in agreement with the rate laws :

$$-d[\text{MnO}_4^-]/dt = k_2 [\text{MnO}_4^-]_t [\text{S}]_0 \quad (2)$$

$$k_{obs} = k_2 [\text{S}]_0 \quad (3)$$

where k_2 is second order rate constant, $[\text{MnO}_4^-]_t$ is the

concentration of permanganate at time t and $[\text{S}]_0$ is the initial concentration of reductant. Some selected values of k_2 are given in Table 1. In case of both the reductants, the rate increased on increasing $[\text{H}^+]$. However, in the absence of added acid no reaction occurred. The reaction rate was unaffected by an increase in ionic strength with LiClO₄(0.1–1.0 mol L⁻¹). The values of apparent activation energies are 40 ± 2 and 65 ± 2 kJ mol⁻¹ for Nic and Inic, respectively.

Discussion

Since the oxidation study on nicotinic acid covered a much wider range of $[\text{H}^+]$ (1×10^{-5} –1.0 mol L⁻¹), the results of this study are discussed first. In aqueous solutions, the nicotinic acid undergoes acid-base equilibria (4-5).

Since in the absence of added acid no reaction occurs, species [A] must be unreactive. The reported values of K_1 and K_2 (Table 2) indicate the formation of species [B] to be complete at $[\text{H}^+] \approx 2 \times 10^{-3}$ mol L⁻¹, and of species [C] at $[\text{H}^+] \approx 0.1$ mol L⁻¹. Since the rate continuously increases on increasing $[\text{H}^+]$, both N-protonated species [B] and [C] appear to be reactive as found earlier¹. Since formation of [C] is almost complete at ~ 0.1 mol L⁻¹ $[\text{H}^+]$, an increase in the rate on increasing $[\text{H}^+]$ beyond 0.1 mol L⁻¹ can not be due to equilibrium (5), and that signals the introduction of a new oxidation pathway involving protonated manganese(vii) species, HMnO₄ (eq. (6)), as discussed earlier by us¹ and others¹⁰⁻¹³.

On the other hand, in the region of high $[H^+]$, nicotinic acid shall be almost fully present as [C] and, therefore, inequality, $K_1 K_2 [H^+]^2 \gg (1 + K_1 [H^+])$ shall hold. Then, only k - and k_3 -paths would contribute to the rate. Hence, on ignoring k_0 -path in numerator and $(1 + K_1 [H^+])$ term in denominator, the rate law (16) reduces to eq.(18),

$$k_2 = \frac{\{k K_1 K_2 [H^+]^2 + k_3 K_1 K_2 K_3 [H^+]^3\}}{\{K_1 K_2 [H^+]^2\}} = k + k_3 K_3 [H^+] \quad (18)$$

From the plot of k_2 versus $[H^+]$ (eq. (18)), the values of k and $k_3 K_3$ were obtained (Table 2). For treatment of the rate data in the middle pH-range (1.42–3.1), the species [A] can be ignored and then the rate law (18) would reduce to eq. (19), which on rearrangement would become eq. (20),

$$k_2 = \frac{\{k_0 K_1 [H^+] + k K_1 K_2 [H^+]^2 + k_3 K_1 K_2 K_3 [H^+]^3\}}{\{K_1 [H^+] + K_1 K_2 [H^+]^2\}} \quad (19)$$

$$k_2 = k_0 K_2 \{(k + k_3 K_3 [H^+] - k_2) [H^+]\} \quad (20)$$

Using the experimental values of k_2 and the values of k_0 , k and $k_3 K_3$ determined from Figs. 1 and 2, the plot of k_2 versus $\{(k + k_3 K_3 [H^+] - k_2) [H^+]\}$ was drawn (Fig. 3). From the intercept and slope of Fig. 3, the values of k_0 and K_2 were determined (Table 2). As discussed in a review earlier², by working over an extended $[H^+]$ -range and with reasonable approximations it has been possible to solve the rate law (16) and determine the values of rate constants, k_0 , k and $k_3 K_3$ and equilibrium constants, K_1 and K_2 . The values of K_1 and K_2 determined by kinetics are in good agreement with those reported in the literature (Table 2). The values of k_0 determined from Figs. 1 and 3 are also in good agreement.

The nature of rate law and $[H^+]$ -dependence in case of both Nic and Inic points to a common mechanism and, therefore, a similar mechanism can be written for Inic also. However, an analysis of $[H^+]$ -dependence in case of Inic showed both [A] and [B] type species to be unreactive. Since, its solution had to be made in 2×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹ HClO₄ solution, the lowest $[H^+]$ that could be studied was 3×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹. In the HClO₄ range of 0.1–1.0 mol L⁻¹, the data fitted the eq. (18), and from the plot in Fig. 2 accordingly, the values of k and $k_3 K_3$ were determined (Table 2). K_1 and K_2 values indicate that in the region, 3×10^{-2} – 0.08×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹ $[H^+]$,

Fig. 3. The plot of k_2 versus $\{(k + k_3 K_3 [H^+] - k_2) [H^+]\}$ for nicotinic acid and isonicotinic acid (eq. (20)).

only [B] and [C] type species would be present and hence the rate data were fitted to eq. (20) (Fig. 3). Interestingly, the plot of k_2 versus $\{(k + k_3 K_3 [H^+] - k_2) [H^+]\}$ was a straight line passing through origin showing the value of k_0 to be zero and, therefore, species [B] to be unreactive (Fig. 3). The value of K_2 obtained from eq. (20) is given in Table 2. Thus, the kinetics of isonicotinic acid oxidation in the $[H^+]$ -range, 0.03–1.0 mol L⁻¹ is in conformity with the rate law (21),

$$k_2 = \frac{\{k K_2 [H^+] + k_3 K_2 K_3 [H^+]^2\}}{\{1 + K_2 [H^+]\}} \quad (21)$$

In the $[H^+]$ -range 0.1–1.0 mol L⁻¹, eq. (21) becomes eq. (18) due to the operation of the inequality $K_2 [H^+] \gg 1$, as discussed in case of Nic.

A comparison of k_2 values shows the oxidation of nicotinic acid to be faster than the oxidation of isonicotinic acid. Likewise, nicotinamide was found to be more reactive than isonicotinamide¹ and hence, the reactivity trend of Nic and Inic can be explained similarly^{1,14–16}. In case of both acids, [C] form appears to be not only the most reactive but also the only one to react with HMnO₄. Thus, the protonation appears to play a major role in enhancing the reactivity of amides and acids of pyridine. A comparison of rate constants reported in this paper and earlier¹, shows the order of relative reactivity of pyridine amides and acids to be : isonicotinamide \approx isonicotinic acid < nicotinamide < nicotinic acid.

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